

СЎЗ САЊАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

5 ЖИЛД, 5 СОН

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА

ТОМ 5, НОМЕР 5

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

VOLUME 5, ISSUE 5

СЎЗ САНЪАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА | INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

№5 (2022) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-9297-2022-5>

Бош муҳаррир:
Тўхтасинов Илҳом
п.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Бош муҳаррир ўринбосари:

Главный редактор:
Тухтасинов Илхом
д.п.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Заместитель главного редактора:

Editor in Chief:
Tuhtasinov Ilhom
DSc. Professor (Uzbekistan)

Deputy Chief Editor

ТАҲРИРИЙ МАСЛАҲАТ КЕНГАШИ

Назаров Бахтиёр
академик. (Ўзбекистон)

Якуб Умарўғли
ф.ф.д., профессор (Туркия)

Алмаз Улви Биннатова
ф.ф.д., профессор (Озарбайжон)

Бокиева Гуландом
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Миннуллин Ким
ф.ф.д., профессор (Татаристон)

Махмудов Низомиддин
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Керимов Исмаил
ф.ф.д., профессор (Россия)

Жўраев Маматкул
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Куренов Рахиммаед
к.ф.н. (Туркменистон)

Кристофер Жеймс Форт
Мичиган университети (АҚШ)

Умархўжаев Мухтор
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Мирзаев Ибодулло
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Болтабоев Ҳамидулла
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Дўстмухаммедов Хуршид
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Лиходзиевский А.С.
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Сиддикова Ирода
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Шиукашвили Тамар
ф.ф.д. (Грузия)

Юсупов Ойбек
масбул котиб, доцент (Ўзбекистон)

РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ СОВЕТ

Назаров Бахтиёр
академик. (Узбекистан)

Якуб Умар оглы
д.ф.н., профессор (Туркия)

Алмаз Улви Биннатова
д.ф.н., профессор (Азербайджан)

Бакиева Гуландом
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Миннуллин Ким
д.ф.н., профессор (Татарстан)

Махмудов Низомиддин
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Керимов Исмаил
д.ф.н., профессор (Россия)

Джураев Маматкул
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Куренов Рахыммаед
к.ф.н. (Туркменистан)

Кристофер Жеймс Форт
Университет Мичигана (США)

Умархаджаев Мухтар
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Мирзаев Ибодулло
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Балтабоев Ҳамидулла
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Дустмухаммедов Хуршид
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Лиходзиевский А.С.
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Сиддикова Ирода
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Шиукашвили Тамар
д.ф.н. (Грузия)

Юсупов Ойбек
отв. секретарь, доцент (Узбекистан)

EDITORIAL BOARD

Bakhtiyor Nazarov
academician. (Uzbekistan)

Yakub Umarogli
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Turkey)

Almaz Ulvi Binnatova
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Azerbaijan)

Bakieva Gulandom
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Minnulin Kim
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Tatarstan)

Mahmudov Nizomiddin
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Kerimov Ismail
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Russia)

Juraev Mamatkul
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Kurenov Rakhimmamed
Ph.D. Ass. Prof. (Turkmenistan)

Christopher James Fort
University of Michigan (USA)

Umarkhodjaev Mukhtar
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Mirzaev Ibodulla
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Boltaboev Hamidulla
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Dustmuhammedov Khurshid
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Lixodzievsky A.S.
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Siddiqova Iroda
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Shiukashvili Tamar
Doc. of philol. scien. (Georgia)

Yusupov Oybek
Ass. prof. (Uzbekistan) - Senior Secretary

PageMaker | Верстка | Саҳифаловчи: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

1. Джалилова Зарнигор Обидовна НУТҚ ҲАРАКАТЛАРИДА ХУШМУОМАЛАЛИКНИНГ ГЕНДЕР ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ.....	5
2. Madiyor Fatilloev SHANOV UD-DIN ABU ABDULLOH YOQUT IBN ABDULLOH AL-HAMAVIY AR-RUMIY AL-BAG‘DODIY HAYOT VA IJOD YO‘LI.....	11
3. Бакаев Нажмиддин Бакаевич ОСНОВОПОЛАГАЮЩИЕ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКИ ПРЕДМЕТА ЛАТИНСКОГО ЯЗЫКА В МЕЖДИСЦИПЛИНАРНОМ РАЗРЕЗЕ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ В ВУЗАХ.....	15
4. Davlatova Muhayyo Hasnovna NUTQ TUZILMALARI MAZMUNIDAGI SEMANTIKA VA PRAGMATIKANING MUNOSABATI.....	21
5. Наширова Шахноза Буриевна ХОРИЖИЙ ТИЛЛАРНИ ЎРГАТИШДА ИККИ ТИЛЛИ ЎҚУВ ЛУҒАТЛАРГА ЭҲТИЁЖНИНГ ОРТИШИ.....	26
6. Mirzayeva Aziza Shavkatovna ADABIYOTSHUNOSLIKDA INTERTEKSTUALLIK VA UNING ELEMENTLARIDAN BIRI IQTIBOS TUSHUNCHASI.....	34
7. Shapsanova Feruza Muzaffarovna PHILOSOPHICAL ASPECTS PRESENTED IN IRIS MURDOCH’S NOVEL “THE SANDCASTLE”.....	39
8. Normurodov Oybek Berdimurod o‘g‘li SAYYID QOSIMIY VA TASAVVUF.....	44
9. Begmatova Dilnoza Muxtarovna, Mamayoqubova Shahlo Oblaqulovna OLIY TA‘LIM MUASSASI O‘QITUVCHI KASSIYASINI ARTTIRISHNING PEDAGOGIK SHARTLARI.....	49
10. Даниёрова Барчиной Абсаттаровна XIX-XX АСР ФРАНЦУЗ АДАБИЙ ЭРТАКЛАРИ.....	55
11. Кулдашова Н. Б. ТИЛШУНОСЛИҚДА ТЕРМИНОЛОГИЯНИНГ ТАЛҚИНИ.....	60
12. Мухиддинова Дилафруз Мансуровна ПАРАДОКС БАТЛЕРА О МАШИНАХ.....	66
13. Nargiza Amirqulova INGLIZ VA O‘ZBEK TILLARI FRAZELOGIYASIDA QO‘SHMA SO‘ZLARINING YASALISHI.....	71
14. Zubaydova Nilufar Nematillaevna SYNTACTIC LINKS CREATED BY PROFESSOR A.M. MUKHIN.....	77
15. Kushatova Nargiza Rustamovna H. G. UELLS VA OLDOS HAKLINING ILMIY FANTASTIKA JANRIGA QO‘SHGAN HISSASI VA UNING QISQACHA TAHLILI.....	83
16. Шохсанам Муҳаммаджонова ТЕЛЕЖУРНАЛИСТИК МАТНЛАРИНИНГ ПСИХОЛИНГВИСТИК ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ.....	87
17. Ergashova Vaxora Sayfillo qizi O‘ZBEK VA ITALYAN BOLALAR ADABIYOTIDA QAHRAMONLAR XARAКТERLARINING QIYOSIY TAHLIL METODI ASOSIDA YORITILISHI.(J.RODARI VA X.TO‘XTABOYEV IJODI ASOSIDA).....	93
18. Муротова Дилноза Хасан қизи УЗР СЎРАШ НУТҚИЙ АКТИНИНГ ТУРЛИ КОНЦЕПТОСФЕРАЛАРДА ИФОДАЛАНИШИ.....	97
19. Махаммадов Бобир Исан ўғли ИНГЛИЗ ТИЛИДАГИ АНДРОИД ОПЕРАЦИОН ТИЗИМИ МОБИЛЬ ИЛОВАЛАРИ (АОТМИ) ТЕРМИНЛАРИНИНГ СЕМАНТИК ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ.....	102

20. Сабина Авазжоновна Махмудова Ж. ОЛДРИЖНИНГ «I DON’ T WANT HIM TO DIE» (“МЕН УНИНГ ЎЛИШНИ ХОҲЛАМАЙМАН”) РОМАНИДАГИ “ЎЗИНИКИ /БЕГОНА” КОНСЕПТУАЛ ҚАРАМА-ҚАРШИЛИГИНИ “БОШҚА – ЎЗИНИКИ – ДЎСТ” ТРИАДАСИГА АЙЛАНТИРИШ.....	108
21. Dalieva Madina Khabibullaevna THEORETICAL FEATURES OF POLYSEMY IN LINGUISTIC TEXTS.....	114
22. Кулиева Дилшода Алижон кизи “КОДЕКС КУМАНИКУС” ҚЎЛЁЗМАСИ ЎРГАНИЛИШ ТАРИХИ.....	121
23. Ашуров Мўмин Умаржонович КОГНИТИВ ТИЛШУНОСЛИК ЯНГИ ЙЎНАЛИШ СИФАТИДА ВА УНИНГ ДОЛЗАРБ МАСАЛАЛАРИ....	130
24. Ҳамраев Дилшод Ҳамдамович “ТАРКИБАДАХШОН” ДОСТОНИ СЮЖЕТИНИНГ ГЕНЕЗИСИ ВА БАДИИЙ ЭВОЛЮЦИЯСИ.....	137
25. Mahkamova Shohida Rahmatullayevna TA’LIM JARAYONIDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA KLASTER TIZIMI.....	143
26. Қурбонов Бобур Чоршанбиевич “МАЖОЛИС УН-НАФОИС”НИНГ ДАРИЙ ТИЛИДАГИ ТАРЖИМАСИ ХУСУСИДА.....	147
27. Умед Караев ЭНГ ҚАДИМИЙ АДАБИЙ ЁДГОРЛИКЛАР АЙРИМ НАМУНАЛАРИ ҲАҚИДА.....	152
28. Пулатова Диёра Фарход кизи ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ И РАЗВИТИЕ АМЕРИКАНСКОЙ ПОЛИТИЧЕСКОЙ САТИРИЧЕСКОЙ ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ.....	160
29. Расулева Нигина Алишеровна ҒАРБ ВА ХИТОЙ АДАБИЁТИДА ИЛМИЙ ФАНТАСТИКА ЖАНРИ: ЎХШАШЛИК ВА МУШТАРАКЛИК.....	169
30. Астанова Гулнора Аминовна МИСР ҲИКОЯТЛАРИДА ШАРҚОНА МЕНТАЛИТЕТ.....	176
31. Абулкасимова Нодира Мирзакаримовна РОЛЬ ЭВФЕМИЗМОВ В РЕПРЕЗЕНТАЦИИ КОНЦЕПТА “WAR”.....	182
32. Саримсоков Сирожиддин Шойзоқович АСПЕКТУАЛ СЕМАНТИКАНИНГ ТАВСИФИ ХУСУСИДА.....	193
33. Хотамова Парвина Илхомовна ҚАРДОШ БЎЛМАГАН ТИЛЛАР ТИЗИМИДА СУБСТАНЦИАЛ ПОСЕССИВ ВА КВАЛИФИКАТИВ ПОСЕССИВ СИНТАКСЕМАЛАРНИ ФАРҚЛАШ УСУЛЛАРИ.....	199

ISSN: 2181-9297

www.tadqiqot.uz

Dalievna Madina KhabibullaevnaSenior teacher, head of the English Methodology Department,
Uzbekistan State University of World Languages**THEORETICAL FEATURES OF POLYSEMY IN LINGUISTIC TEXTS** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7038197>**ABSTRACT**

The article describes issues based on analyzing the significance of polysemy in linguistics and its meanings in different contexts. In the process of language development, when a word is used in various contexts, modifications of its meaning appear - lexico-semantic variants. This process is called polysemy or polysemy (the semantic property of a word to have several meanings at the same time). Polysemy of a word is the presence of one or more meanings in a word. This is the ability of one word to serve to designate different objects and phenomena of reality.

Key words: language, phenomena of reality, polysemy, meaning.

Далиева Мадина ХабибуллаевнаСтарший преподаватель,
заведующая кафедрой методики английского языка,
Узбекский государственный университет мировых языков**ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПОЛИСЕМИИ В ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИХ
ТЕКСТАХ****АННОТАЦИЯ**

В статье рассматриваются вопросы, основанные на анализе значения многозначных слов в языкознании и их значения в разных контекстах. Известно, что в процессе развития языка при употреблении слова в разных контекстах его значение меняется - появляются лексико-семантические варианты. Этот процесс называется полисемией (семантическое свойство слова иметь несколько значений одновременно). Многозначность слова – это наличие в слове одного или нескольких значений. И это способность одного слова определять разные предметы и события действительности.

Ключевые слова: язык, явления действительности, многозначность, значение.

Dalievna Madina XabibullaevnaO'zbekiston davlat jahon tillari universiteti
ingliz tili metodikasi kafedrasini mudiri, Katta o'qituvchi**POLISEMIYANING TILSHUNOSLIK MATNLARIDAGI O'ZIGA XOS NAZARIY
XUSUSIYATLARI**

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada ko'p ma'noli so'zlarning tilshunoslikdagi ahamiyati va uning turli kontekstlardagi ma'nolari tahlil etilgan. Ma'lumki, til taraqqiyoti jarayonida so'z turli kontekstlarda qo'llanilganda uning ma'nosi o'zgarishi - leksik-semantik variantlari paydo bo'ladi. Bu jarayon polisemiya deb ataladi (so'zning bir vaqtning o'zida bir nechta ma'noga ega bo'lish semantik xususiyati). So'zning ko'p ma'noliligi - so'zda bir yoki bir nechta ma'noning mavjudligidir. Bu esa birgina so'zning voqelikning turli ob'ektlari va hodisalarini belgilashga xizmat qilish qobiliyatidir.

Kalit so'zlar: til, voqelik hodisalari, ko'p ma'nolilik, ma'no.

INTRODUCTION

The phenomenon of polysemy takes place in many language systems. Despite all the richness of the Russian language, polysemy is quite common in it. For example, the word "key" has the meanings 1) means for opening locks; 2) spring, source; 3) musical key. And the word "onion" has the following meanings: 1) a plant; 2) a weapon that shoots arrows; 3) (youth slang) appearance. It should be noted that the Russian language has the lowest polysemy. In English, polysemy is much more pronounced. When translating English-language texts and communicating, it is often extremely difficult to find the correct meaning. It is the ambiguity of words that is the most common cause of translation errors, ridiculous interpretations and misunderstandings in personal communication. Based on the foregoing, we can conclude that the topic put forward by the author for consideration and research is extremely relevant for the English language and for people who study it, since English has the highest polysemy of words. And knowing all the meanings of words is a necessary condition for successful communication and understanding of the literature being read. The linguistic name of this phenomenon is 'polysemy': from the Greek words 'poly' - 'many' and 'sema' - 'meaning'. This very polysemy leads to our mistakes, misunderstanding and misinterpretation. Despite the fact that the history of the study of polysemy has more than one decade, today it is impossible to speak unambiguously about a constructive solution to this issue. The appearance in the last years of the 20th century of studies related to a comprehensive analysis of this linguistic phenomenon is an important stage in the formulation of the problems of polysemy as a linguistic phenomenon.

DISCUSSIONS

The phenomenon of polysemy, as Maslova notes, "has a cognitive nature and is due to the complex interaction of linguistic factors, the psychophysiological and social nature of a person".

Speaking of lexical polysemy, it should be borne in mind that in the Russian linguistic tradition there are several synonymous terms for naming this phenomenon: polysemy, polysemy, semantic derivation, ambiguity. The broadest term is polysemy. It assumes that a language unit has more than one meaning. The term polysemy is sometimes used as a synonym for polysemy, while polysemy is usually understood only as lexical polysemy. This difference is found in the functioning of the corresponding adjectives: only a word can be polysemic, while both an expression and a statement can be polysemous.

Note that polysemic words with different shades of meaning most often have a common seme. Modern linguistics distinguishes lexical and grammatical polysemy. An example of grammatical polysemy is the use of verbs in the form of the 3rd person plural in indefinitely personal sentences, for example, "they count chickens in the fall", as well as the forms of the 2nd person plural in their own personal and generalized meaning. (Compare "you can't make out the handwriting" and "you take things apart - you go for a walk").

In the case of lexical polysemy, the implementation of one or another meaning of the word is also carried out by a wider context or situation, the general theme of speech. For example, the noun "field" has the following lexical meanings: 1) treeless space; 2) land cultivated for crops; 3) a flat area specially equipped for something; 4) the space within which the action of some forces is manifested (special); 5) (pl.) a blank strip along the edge of a book, manuscript; 6) (pl.) brim of a hat.

This phenomenon is associated with the ability of one word to serve to designate different objects and phenomena of reality, associatively related to each other and forming a complex semantic

unity. It is the presence of a common semantic feature that distinguishes polysemy from homonymy and homophony.

Observing the types of figurative meanings, we were once again convinced that the meanings of a polysemantic word are interconnected and form a hierarchically arranged semantic structure. In these relations, the systemic nature of vocabulary at the level of one word (epidigmatic) is manifested. The meanings of a polysemant can be related in different ways, so E.P. Pustoshilo distinguishes the following types of polysemy: radial, chain and mixed.

One cannot but agree that homonymy and polysemy are different concepts. But it is impossible not to recognize that these concepts have a common feature - the difference in meanings with the identity of the form. This allows them to be combined into a broader concept of ambiguity.

The difficulty of distinguishing between polysemy and homonymy leads some scientists to the assertion that "it is advisable to consider only words that are different in origin as homonyms." However, firstly, not in all cases it is possible to establish the origin of the word, and secondly, and secondly, - and this is the main thing - following such an attitude would move the concept of homonymy to the field of historical lexicology, while it is for modern languages that one has to distinguish between meanings related to one with the other, and the meanings, which, although expressed by the same sound form, have nothing in common semantically. This is a question not only of linguistic theory, but also of lexicographic practice.

The problem of distinguishing between homonymy and polysemy can arise when homonyms appear as a result of the semantic splitting of a polysemantic word. At the same time, completely different words are formed on the basis of different meanings of one word. Their former semantic connections are lost, and only an etymological analysis allows us to establish a once common semantic feature, indicating their common historical root. For example, as a result of the collapse of a polysemantic word, homonyms appeared: scolding - scolding and scolding - war, battle; Wednesday is the environment and Wednesday is the day of the week.

However, the divergence of the meanings of a polysemantic word occurs very slowly, and therefore the appearance of homonyms is not always recognized as a completed process. Transitional cases are possible, which can be interpreted in different ways.

Modern science has developed criteria for distinguishing between homonymy and polysemy, helping to separate the meanings of the same word and homonyms that arose as a result of a complete break in polysemy.

According to D.E. Rosenthal, there are three ways to distinguish between homonymy and polysemy: lexical, morphological and semantic.

The lexical method consists in identifying synonymous relationships between homonyms and polysemantics. If consonant units are included in the same synonymous series, then different meanings still retain semantic proximity and, therefore, it is too early to talk about the development of polysemy into homonymy. If they have different synonyms, then we have homonymy. For example, the word *indigenous* in the meaning of "indigenous" has the synonyms *primordial*, *main*; and *root* in the meaning of "fundamental issue" is a synonym for the main one. The words *main* and *main* are synonymous, therefore, we have two meanings of the same word. And here is another example; the word *thin* in the meaning of "not well-fed" forms a synonymous series with adjectives *skinny*, *frail*, *lean*, *dry*, and *thin* - "devoid of positive qualities" - with adjectives *bad*, *nasty*, *bad*. The words *skinny*, *feeble*, etc. are not synonymous with the words *bad*, *nasty*. This means that the lexical units under consideration are independent, i.e., homonymous.

According to our observations, these terms in dictionaries "acquire an abstract character, combine an indefinite number of denotations, generating the emergence of polysemy" [2, p. 85]; however, these words will be related to a certain denotation only in the context, in the process of their functioning. On the example of the work of A. A. Potebnya "Thought and Language", G. V. Mayorov observes how the term word correlates with many denotations, that is, it is broad-meaningful. It can be seen from the above quotation that the semantics of the linguistic term word is much broader in the context of the work of A. A. Potebnya; the definition from the lexicographic source is only the tip of the lexico-semantic "iceberg", because in scientific discourse the term word as a linguistic unit

reveals such conceptual meanings as: “language”, “work of art”, “thought” and many other metaphorical and associative rethinking.

From another point of view, broad meaning is only the content of the most general, abstract lexico-semantic variant of a polysemantic word. In our opinion, such a vision of broad meaning is fully justified, because in linguistic terminology one can find examples of “such” wide meaning terms. Compare, for example, the meaning of terms in which broad-based LSVs are underlined: language is “a complex social phenomenon in which the following features are distinguished: a) the most important means of human communication and uniting people into a community; b) a means of self-identification and expression of the mentality of the nation (ethnos); c) a means of forming and developing thought, carrying out cognitive activity, realizing the spiritual culture of the people”, “a system of socially conscious sound and reproduced in writing signs that function according to a certain regulation, norms and are realized in the sound and semantic substance of specific speech acts of communication”, “a certain information system that performs the function of a natural language or functions as its substitute”, morphological category - “a category of words united by the same forms of expression of grammatical meanings”; “a generalized grammatical characteristic of a certain category of words, expressed in the ratio of the forms of words of this category or in opposition to the grammatical forms of the same word”; “affixal varieties of words expressing the grammatical categories of this category of words.

The phenomenon of polysemy takes place in many language systems. Despite all the richness of the Russian language, polysemy is quite common in it. For example, the word "key" has the meanings 1) means for opening locks; 2) spring, source; 3) musical key. And the word "onion" has the following meanings: 1) a plant; 2) a weapon that shoots arrows; 3) (youth slang) appearance. It should be noted that the Russian language has the lowest polysemy. In English, polysemy is much more pronounced. When translating English-language texts and communicating, it is often extremely difficult to find the correct meaning. It is the ambiguity of words that is the most common cause of translation errors, ridiculous interpretations and misunderstandings in personal communication. Based on the foregoing, we can conclude that the topic put forward by the author for consideration and research is extremely relevant for the English language and for people who study it, since English has the highest polysemy of words. And knowing all the meanings of words is a necessary condition for successful communication and understanding of the literature being read. The linguistic name of this phenomenon is 'polysemy': from the Greek words 'poly' - 'many' and 'sema' - 'meaning'. This very polysemy leads to our mistakes, misunderstanding and misinterpretation.

Since many words are both verbs and nouns or even adjectives or adverbs, it is important to understand in which section you should look for the meaning you need.

For example, the noun "*band*" has the following meanings: 1) *a group of people, a detachment*; 2) *orchestra*; 3) *strip, tape, border*; 4) *range*; 5) *gang, flock*; 6) *chromosome disk*.

And the well-known word "*spring*" is translated as: 1) *весна*; 2) *родник*; 3) *пружина*; 4) *упругость*; 5) *прыжок*; 6) *появляться*.

The second most important component of any sentence is the verb. And they are the ones with the most value.

For example, the verb "get" is the subject of research by many English and Russian linguists, as it ranks second in terms of the number of meanings. In modern English it has the following meanings:

Start of Ownership: *Next day is the only way to get a ticket.*

Owning something: *You've got a perfect car.*

Movement: *Without using any money, some of escapees got as far as North Wales and Scotland.*

Permission: *You may not get to attend client meetings.*

Commitment: *You've got to look at evidence, that's what you've got to do!*

Passivity: *Well, we got caught, of cause, by this Mr. Smith.*

State Start: *Sometimes students set anxious about this, and believe they are not making audience contact early enough.*

By attaching adverbs and prepositions to itself, it becomes a phrasal verb and, at the same time, is very difficult for foreigners to understand.

For example:

«get about» - 1) свободно передвигаться; 2) путешествовать; 3) вновь двигаться после болезни; 4) распространяться (о новостях);

«get across» - становиться известным

«get back» - вернуться;

«get away» - уезжать;

«get at» - 1) добираться; 2) выяснять что-либо;

«get of», «get for» etc.

This verb can be used with almost all currently existing prepositions, in each case taking on different meanings.

Polysemy takes place among all parts of speech: adjectives, adverbs and even function words.

The adjective "capital" in translation from English has the following meanings: 1) капитальный, основной; 2) главный; 3) превосходный; 4) заглавный (о букве); 5) юр. уголовный (о преступлении); 6) смертный (о приговоре, казни).

The above examples confirm that there are a certain number of words in the English language, and ten times more concepts. This phenomenon of polysemy is a significant difficulty and even an obstacle in the process of communication and cognition.

Context has a decisive influence on the characterization of the meaning of a word. Usually, situational and speech (linguistic) contexts are distinguished. Situational context is the situation in which communication takes place. For example, the word "ring" can mean both a ring and a phone ring. If the speaker pronounces this word and the phone rings, then it is clear what is being said. This is a situational context. The linguistic context is a complex lexical and grammatical phenomenon. It includes not only the meanings of all neighboring words, but also all grammatical relations in a particular speech segment.

Since polysemy is closely related to the presence of a common semantic and semantic connection, let us consider its types that arise as a result of the transfer of meanings as a result of the emergence of associative links.

Depending on what is the basis of associative links - connection, adjacency of phenomena or the commonality of some of their features and the resulting similarity - there are metonymic and metaphorical transfers of meanings and, as their varieties, synecdoche and functional transfer. It is these linguistic phenomena that most influence the possibility of expressing expression with the help of polysemy.

Metonymy is a type of semantic change in which the transfer of the name of one or another object or phenomenon to another object or phenomenon is carried out on the basis of real (and sometimes imaginary) connections between the corresponding objects or phenomena. For example:

1. Animal - animal meat: for example, fowl - 1) poultry, especially, chicken,

2) poultry meat, persons, chicken meat; goose - 1) goose, goose,

2) goose;

2. Tree - the wood of this tree: for example, pine - 1) bot. Pine (Pinus),

2) pine wood; oak - 1) bot. oak (Quercus gen.),

2) oak wood; maple - 1) bot. maple (Acer gen.),

2) maple wood, etc. (cf. Russian birch, spruce, cedar, aspen, pine, etc.),

3. Material - a product made from this material: for example, bronze - 1) bronze,

2) a bronze item; clay - 1) clay, alumina,

2) clay pipe; silver - 1) silver,

2) silverware, etc. (cf. Russian | bronze, plaster, gold, glass, silver, etc.).

4. Content - content: for example, school - 1) school, schoolchildren; educational institution,

2) collected. school students; hall - 1) a college or university building intended for meetings

or classes;

2) students living or studying in this building; house - 1) house, building,

- 2) family, genus; house, dynasty,
- 3) theater, cinema,
- 4) public, spectators, etc. (cf. Russian audience, hall, class, factory, etc.).
5. Property - the subject of property: for example, authority - 1) authority, weight, influence,
2) authority, major specialist; beauty - 1) beauty, beautiful;
2) beauty; talent - 1) talent, gift, giftedness;
2) a talented person, talent, etc. (cf. Russian genius, mediocrity, authority, insignificance, etc.).
6. Action - the subject of the action: for example, support - 1) support, help,
2) support, stronghold;
3) the breadwinner; supply - 1) temporary replacement of a position,
2) temporary deputy;

"It is known that every sixth meaning of frequency nouns included in the first thousand frequency words is the result of metonymic transfer" [3, C.64].

Metonymic transfers are characteristic not only of nouns, but also of words of other parts of speech: adjectives and verbs (for example, green - 1) green, green;

- 2) unripe, unripe, green; blind - 1) blind, blind;
- 2) intended for the blind;

A variety of metonymy, often interpreted as a separate type of semantic change, is synecdoche. Representing the transfer of a name from part to whole head - 1) head;

- 2) a person;
- 3) head of cattle;

4) herd; a flock (of birds), etc.) or from a whole to a part (for example, doctor - 1) mouth. mentor, teacher, pundit;

- 2) doctor (academic degree);

3) doctor, doctor; Synecdoche stands out as a separate type of transfer because it is based on logical connections. With synecdoche, the circle of referents denoted by the word changes: the name of a narrower set is used to denote a wider set of objects in which the narrow set is only an integral part, and vice versa: the designation of a wide set becomes the designation of its individual subsets. In the linguistic literature, this process is also described as an expansion and narrowing of meanings [3, c.52].

It should be noted, however, that the effect of intralinguistic causes is not as obvious as the influence of extralinguistic factors that cause the appearance of ambiguity, and much less has been studied as a result.

Just as the causes of semantic changes can be, as shown above, very different, semantic changes themselves can also differ in nature, because they can be based on different patterns. In other words, the use of the name of some object to refer to some other object is not chaotic. The secondary use of names, usually described as the transfer of meanings, although it is undoubtedly more correct to speak of the transfer of names and the development of secondary meanings in them, is based on the laws of associations. They determine the types of semantic changes of the word in the course of its historical development, the types of relationships between meanings in diachrony and, as an end result, the types of meanings themselves in the semantic structure of a polysemantic word.

CONCLUSION

Thus, the great importance of polysemy for the possibility of expressing subjective attitudes and feelings, creating a sense of ambiguity, poetry, irony or hidden meaning in the English language is explained by the fact that this language is concise and inflectional.

Most of the words in it can be used as different parts of speech, and this determines the need for stylistic coloring of speech or text. Also, a large number of phrasal verbs play a special role in the development of grammatical and lexical polysemy. The development of polysemy was also affected by multiple borrowings, which can now also be used to give the text additional meaning.

Polysemy makes it possible to express the author's attitude to the spoken or written text, since it is polysemy that allows the most accurate and complete understanding of the context.

Particularly important for achieving the emotionality of speech are such variants of polysemy as metaphor and metonymy, as well as the function of transference and synecdoche. Speech using these polysemic structures becomes more emotional and figurative, acquires an individual character and colloquial coloring. In fiction, polysemic structures can be used to create an ironic context due to the presence of additional meaning. Polysemy makes it possible to play with meaning and most clearly contributes to the expression of expression.

References:

1. Amosova N.N. Fundamentals of English phraseology. - L., 1963. - 206 p.
2. Arnold I.V. Lexicology of modern English. - 3rd ed. M., 1986. - 296 p.
3. Blokh M.Ya., Aralov A.M. Aspects of the meaning of the word // Semantics and functioning of the English verb. - Gorky, 1985. - P. 15-29.
4. Grosul L.Ya. On the question of the polysemy and broad meaning of English words. 1989. - P. 3–9.
5. Dimova S.N. On the polyfunctionality of a word with a broad meaning (on the material of the English noun way): Author. dis. ... cand. philol. sciences: 10.02.04. - M., 1972. - S. 10.
6. Zhukova T.V. To the question of the definition in the paradigmatic aspect of words with the most common lexical meanings // Problems of Linguistics. - 1987. - No. 2. – P.85 – 95.
7. Kolobaev V.K. On some related phenomena in the field of vocabulary (On the question of the relationship between polysemy and broad meaning of a word) // Foreign languages at school. - 1983. - No. 1. - P. 11–13.
8. Kudrevatykh L.P. Monosemia: narrow meaning - wide meaning // Issues of German Philology. – Kirov, 1997. P. 35–40.
9. Mayorov G.V. Metallexeme “Word” in A.A. Potebny’s book “Thought and Language” // Vestnik Mosk. un - that. - Ser. 9. - 2010. - No. 1. - P. 174–182.
10. Nikitin M.V. Polysemy at the limit (wide-ranging) // Conceptual space of language: Sat. scientific tr. Dedicated to the anniversary of Professor Nikolai Nikolaevich Boldyrev / Ed. prof. E.S. Kubryakova; Federal Agency for Education, Tamb. state un-t im. G.R. Derzhavin. Tambov, 2005, pp. 101–111.
11. Plotkin V.Ya. The structure of the English language. - M., 1989. - 240 p.

СЎЗ САЊАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

5 ЖИЛД, 5 СОН

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА

ТОМ 5, НОМЕР 5

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

VOLUME 5, ISSUE 5